

Consent Form - TCLE

Dear Participant,

You are being invited to take part in a research study for data collection. We kindly ask for your participation in this study, which aims to evaluate methods for teaching Micro Frontends. Please note that your participation in this research is entirely voluntary.

1) Proceedings

The participant will be invited to complete a profile characterization form and take part in tasks involving the identification and solution of problems in Micro Frontend architectures. At the end, the participant will answer a feedback questionnaire about the research. Your personal data will be kept confidential throughout the entire study. The results will be anonymized and may be published in a scientific article, along with quantitative and qualitative analyses.

2) Confidentiality of the Research

The data collected during this study will be used strictly for research purposes and will not be employed in any form of professional or personal evaluation. All information collected in this study is confidential, and your name and the name of your organization will not be identified in any way, unless explicit authorization is given for that purpose.

3) Costs and Benefits

This research aims to propose tools and methods for the evaluation and evolution of Micro Frontend architectures. Based on the data obtained, we aim to identify common problems and propose effective solutions, thereby building a knowledge base that guides developers and software architects in implementing Micro Frontends. All research involving human subjects entails some level of risk. In this study, participants will not incur any cost or burden for their participation and will not receive any form of reimbursement or compensation for taking part.

4) Participation

You are being invited to participate because of your technical knowledge about Micro Frontend architectures, whether acquired through industry experience or academic training. Your participation in this study is very important and entirely voluntary. Participants have the right not to take part or to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Participants also have the right to decline to answer any of the questions in the surveys and/or interviews. This document (ICF) will be prepared in two copies, which will be initialed on all pages except the one containing signatures, and signed at the end by both the participant and the lead researcher. Each party will retain one copy.

5) Statement of Consent

I have read or had someone read to me the information contained in this document before signing this informed consent form. I declare that all technical language used to describe this research study was satisfactorily explained and that I received answers to all my questions. I also confirm that I received a copy of this Informed Consent Form. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time, without any penalty. I declare that I am over 18 years of age and give my consent freely and voluntarily to participate in this study.

The researchers responsible for the study are available to provide any clarification or answer questions at any time. Their contact information is as follows:

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Manaus - AM, ____ / ____ / _____

Participant

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